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STATUS OF LOCAL HONEY BEES IN ALGERIA

Stato delle colonie locali di Apis mellifera in Algeria

Honey bees provide essential pollination services by pollinating plants and thereby contributing to nature conservation and food production. Despite their importance, the decline in honey bee populations worldwide is alarming. This decline can be explained by multifactor effects among which climatic conditions, the expansion of pesticides, human practices, diseases, and parasites. As little data is available concerning honey bee in northern Africa (BAROUR *et al.*, 2005; CHARHBAR *et al.*, 2012; LOUCIF-AYAD *et al.*, 2013), a screening of pathogens and viruses was done for the native subspecies of Algeria in northern Africa: *Apis mellifera intermissa* and *Apis mellifera sahariensis*.

The local honey bees were first analyzed using molecular tools: mitochondrial and nuclear DNA (GARNERY *et al.*, 1998a, 1998b). Concerning honey bee health, the screening concerned the mites (*Varroa destructor*, *Acarapis woodi*); microsporidia (*Nosema ceranae*, *Nosema apis*, *Nosema bombi*); protozoa (*Apicystis bombi*, *Crithidia mellificae*) and bacterial (*Paenibacillus larvae*, *Melissococcus plutonius*); pathogens and viruses [Deformed Wing Virus (DWW); Acute Bee Paralysis Virus (ABPV); Israeli Acute Paralysis Virus (IAPV); Kashmir Bee Virus (KBV); Sacbrood Virus (SBV); Lake Sinai Virus (LSV); Slow Bee Paralysis Virus (SBPV); Chronic Bee Paralysis Virus (CBPV); Black Queen Cell Virus (BQCV)].

The analyses provide genetic evidence of the African origin of Algerian honey bee populations and showed that they are characterized by a higher

level of genetic variation (LOUCIF-AYAD *et al.*, 2014; ACHOU *et al.*, 2015). The molecular studies of pathogens in *A.m.intermissa* and *A.m. sabariensis* subspecies revealed the presence of *V. destructor*, *N. ceranae*, *P. larvae*, *A. bombi*, *C. mellificae*. Eight viruses were detected (DWV, ABPV, IAPV, SBV, LSV, SBPV, CBPV, BQCV). In addition, a parasitism of a phorid flies species: *Megaselia scalaris* (Diptera Phoridae) and *Senotainia tricuspis* (Diptera Sarcophagidae) was reported in *A. mellifera intermissa* and we found DWV to be present in adult flies of *M. scalaris* and actively replicating in the fly larvae (LOUCIF-AYAD *et al.*, 2013; HADDAD *et al.*, 2015; MENAIL *et al.*, 2016).

This study confirmed that local populations of honey bees belong to the African lineage (A) and are characterized by a high genetic variability. Despite the presence of multiple virus infections and pathogens in the colonies screened, these colonies showed no obvious clinical signs of diseases. These data will contribute to the improving knowledge concerning bee pathogens and conservation measures will be needed to prevent the loss of these native honey bees and to preserve their biodiversity.

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